

Delamination Characteristics of Laminated Composites Resulting From Instrumented Impact Tests

by

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ABSTRACT

Delamination characteristics of 0.3 cm thick carbon/epoxy laminates were studied. Panels were cut into 15.25 cm square specimens and mounted in the test chamber of a 19 mm diameter light gas gun. Plastic projectiles with flat faces were fired at the center of the panels which were clamped on all four edges. It was found that the projectiles consistently penetrated the specimens, masking any useful information concerning delamination. Lexan[®] backing plates were added to the specimens to retard fracture. The backing plates eliminated projectile penetration as expected, but also created large scale delaminations not observable before. In addition, manganin gages were imbedded in some of the composite panels to provide load histories during impact. This provided information on the normal stresses imparted to the panels. C-scan images were used to determine the size and depth of the delaminated surfaces. It was apparent that this method of impacting the panels created delaminations while very little or no surface fracture was introduced. A separate set of specimens were prepared with artificial delaminations by inserting Teflon[®] strips of similar size and location as those of the impacted specimens. Both the impacted and the artificially delaminated specimens were tested using a compression-after-impact test setup. While the two sets of specimens showed similar performance, it was found that the artificially induced delaminations did not duplicate the behavior of the impacted panels exactly.

Keywords: Composite material, Delamination, Impact studies, Ultrasonic damage assessment

INTRODUCTION

Impact loading of composite materials is known to produce fiber breakage, matrix cracking, and delaminations. While the first two modes of fracture are often detectable from the external surfaces of the composite, this is not always the case with delaminations. They can occur at free edge, or completely included in a specimen. Detection of impact damage has been done primarily by sectioning the specimen, radiography, and ultrasonic analysis. Recently though, ultrasonic methods have been increasingly applied to detect damage and defects within composite materials with satisfactory results [1-3]. The fact that delaminations occur in the plane of the composite laminae makes them ideal for detection by a pulse-echo ultrasonic system which can scan the area of the plate and detect reflected signals. The amplitude and time of flight of these signals can be used to determine the size and depth of delaminations.

Much experimental work has been performed to characterize and study impact induced delaminations [4-12]. Instrumented impact has been a common method to try to correlate projectile mass, velocity, etc. with the locations of included delaminations in specific laminates. Instrumented drop-weight towers are often used, and resulting velocity and load history data has been compared with delamination locations and compression after impact data. Daniel and Wooh [4] used this procedure with strain gages embedded within laminates in an attempt to correlate the dynamic responses with delamination, but found analysis difficult. While drop towers do produce delaminations, other modes of fracture are also created. Even with low velocity impact, permanent dents and hairline ply cracks are commonplace. Thus, it becomes difficult to isolate the effect that delaminations alone have on the residual strength of impacted composites. Ballistic impact experiments have been performed to a lesser degree in order to study the damage characteristics of higher velocity impact. Cantwell [5,6] has studied the effects of high velocity impact on fiber stacking sequences, and compared the specimen response with low velocity impact. While large-scale delaminations can be created using projectiles, it becomes more difficult to analyze the specimens during impact. Measures of the kinetic energy transfer and maximum deflection of laminates have been made by Malvern et al [7] and correlated to delamination area. In the recent past, manganin gages, which are sensitive to normal pressure, have been used to measure dynamic load histories [13,14]. This approach may be useful in understanding the formation process of delaminations within various laminates.

To predict the laws governing propagation of delaminations, the technique of using Teflon[®] or Kapton[®] inserts has been popular. The same procedure has been used to compare "damaged" versus undamaged panels in mechanical tests. Reddy et al [8] conducted a nondestructive study whereby it was found that sizable Teflon[®] inclusions had a negligible effect on the bending and compressive stiffness for some laminates. Results from Chester and Clark [9] indicate that the role of delaminations in the compressive behavior outweighs that of fiber breakage or ply cracks. They used surface-mounted strain gages to compare the compressive response of impacted specimens with specimens containing detailed Teflon[®] modeled damage. Their findings were that carefully placed inserts did closely model the delaminations.

The purpose of this investigation is to focus on the phenomenon of included delamination by minimizing other failure modes within the specimen. An instrumented impact study using Manganin gages to record load history was performed along with ultrasonic evaluation of the specimens. The effects of projectile velocity, load history, and laminate lay-up on the delamination shape, size and location were examined. Teflon[®] inserts were also used to compare the compressive response of panels containing simulated versus real delaminations.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Test specimens with lay-ups of [(0/90)₅/0]_s, [0₃/90₆/0₃]_s, [(0/-45/90/+45)₂]_s, [0₃/-45₃/+45₃/90₃]_s, and [0₃/-45₃/90₃/+45₃]_s were manufactured from Hercules AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy prepreg. Panels 0.6 m square were vacuum bagged, and cured to manufacturer's specifications on a large hot press. After the consolidation, smaller square plates were rough cut from the panels. These were then carefully ground to 15.25 cm lengths, making sure that the edges were square. The corners were rounded off and the plates were labeled prior to ultrasonic examination.

Plates which contained gages or simulated defects were made individually to the 15.25 cm size. Manganin gages supplied from Measurements Group, Inc. [15] were embedded in the manufacture of twelve [0₃/90₆/0₃]_s at the 0₆/90₆ interface. It was necessary that the gages be encapsulated with polyimide to eliminate electrical contact with graphite fibers in the laminate. The gage pattern was centered in the plate with the encapsulated leads extending 3.5 cm. At this point, a solder junction was made with polyimide insulated 0.2 mm dia. wire which was cut off several centimeters beyond the edge of the laminate. The junction was covered on both sides with a small piece of Kapton film, again for insulation. After consolidation, the small wires were soldered to a terminal strip near the edge of the specimen. All gages survived the laminate cure cycle. To create panels with simulated delaminations, c-scans of damaged panels were increased to actual size on transparency film. With the aid of the transparencies and time of flight data, Teflon[®] tape was cut to the proper shape, and laid in the correct location between the laminae. After the panels had been consolidated, they were scanned to verify their resemblance to the original impacted panel.

INSTRUMENTATION

A digital based pulse-echo ultrasonic scanning machine [16] was used for the purpose of nondestructive examination of the specimens. The system is menu driven from a computer for ease of operation. The raw signal amplitude and time of flight data is converted into color images for effective interpretation. Figure 1 illustrates the c-scan of a panel with amplitude information in the center square and time of flight data in the adjacent rectangles. Numerical data can be picked off of the color display with a mouse to discern the locations of the delaminations. The system is capable of dividing a signal into as many as 8 gates to help isolate defects. It stores b and c-scan formatted files and contains additional software for image comparison and image enhancement of data. It has been verified with the use of Teflon® inclusions that the system can resolve defects at all interfaces within the laminates of this study.

A 19mm light-gas gun shown in figure 2 was used to impact the specimens. An optional gunpowder breech was used in these experiments incorporating a modified shotgun shell to propel the projectiles. The 2.1 m long barrel is surrounded by a cylindrical sleeve. Near the exit of the barrel are ports for two velocity pins 20 cm apart and a vacuum port. The velocity pins are triggers for a timing circuit incorporating a light gauge wire protruding about 1 mm into the bore of the barrel. As the projectile passes, the triggers start and stop the timer respectively so that the exit velocity can be calculated within 3 percent error. The vacuum port is an option so that with high velocity experiments an air shock ahead of the projectile will not prematurely trigger the timing circuit. The barrel exits into an enclosed rectangular recovery chamber. Any instrumentation within the recovery chamber is connected via a coaxial bus to the control panel.

Figure 1. Typical C-scan illustrating delamination sizes and locations

Figure 2. Schematic of 19 mm gun used to impact specimens

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

All specimens which were impacted were held in a metal fixture which supported all edges of the panels and exposed the tool side for impact. The projectiles used were 5 cm long machined Lexan[®] cylinders weighing about 17 grams. Several panels were shot at the lowest speeds possible. The result was severe splintering and partial penetration of the panel. The severe fracture scattered c-scan signals, resulting in little information concerning internal delaminations. To retard surface fracture, a Lexan[®] plate was added to the setup to support the back surface of the specimens. This fixture was placed in the target chamber so that the specimen was square to and about 8 cm away from the barrel exit. This arrangement allowed delaminations to be created within most plates with no external damage whatsoever.

Plates containing manganin gages were connected to a Wheatstone bridge via coaxial cable. A digitizing oscilloscope recorded the voltage changes across the bridge during impact. Calibration of the bridge yielded a quadratic relation of output voltage to percent change in gage resistance. The percentage change in gage resistance varies linearly with pressure at the rate of .0027 per Kilobar. As the bridge excitation voltage for manganin gages must be limited to 200 microseconds to prevent thermally induced resistance changes, it was necessary to devise a mechanism to trigger the electronics. Two stripped leads were taped down close together on the panel's surface, immediate over the center. A thin foil was then glued to the front side of the projectile so that it activated the trigger circuit just prior to impact with the front surface of the plate. The voltage waveforms from the oscilloscope were downloaded to a computer and converted into pressure signals. The lead resistance error in the experiment was accounted for.

The impacted specimens were c-scanned again and compared with the original data files. The depth and size of delaminations were determined, and comparisons were made between panel lay-up, velocity of impact, and delamination characteristics. A Boeing Compression After Impact (CAI) test fixture was used in conjunction with an Instron mechanical test machine to further evaluate selected specimens. The fixture was modified so that it could accommodate the square 15.25 cm panels and apply the same boundary conditions as the standard CAI test. All bolts were uniformly torqued down for each test, to prevent the knife-edges from slipping. The specimens were crushed at .015 mm/sec to determine ultimate compressive strengths before and after impact. Panels with simulated delaminations modelling damaged $[0_3/90_6/0_3]_S$ specimens also underwent CAI testing.

RESULTS

Two difficulties were encountered with the instrumented panels. Due to the short times involved in impact, the synchronization of the trigger, gage excitation, and oscilloscope acquisition was critical. The trigger mechanism used worked properly only about seventy-five percent of the time. On other occasions it would tend to trigger prior to impact, resulting in no measured signal. Secondly, not a single gage survived an impact experiment. Gage life often did not extend far beyond the initial shock wave. Figure 3 depicts the load histories obtained for four of the gaged panels impacted. The signal which rises off scale at 35 microseconds is due to gage failure, but the one which goes off scale on the negative side survived longer. It oscillated wildly off the scale of this plot. Figure 4 gives c-scans of these four gaged panels A-D, impacted at velocities of 109, 211, 271, and 313 m/s respectively. The areas of delamination are clearly increasing with the velocity of impact and represent 5, 9, 17, and 27 percent of the total panel areas. A non-planar impact in panel A resulted in asymmetric damage, and elevated the peak pressure to a level comparable with panel B. Comparing the peak pressure with the delaminated area for the latter three panels gives a linear relation. The behavior of the signal immediately after the initial shock wave also seems to have relevance to the degree of delamination in the specimen. Signal A is fairly calm, signal B gently oscillates, and C and D become extremely erratic after the initial shock.

Impact from Lexan[®] projectiles produced no visible damage on the surface of the panels for all velocities under 300 m/s. In excess of this speed, ply cracks would sometimes appear on the front surface of the specimen. Projectile velocities as low as 100 m/s were found to produce internal damage. The damage area for panels in the study were generally conical, as numerous others have reported. That is, the delaminations were larger as one proceeded through the thickness. For the $[(0/90)_5/0]_S$ laminates, c-scans revealed that the greatest damage was located at

or just below center of the laminate. The large number of ply changes made it difficult to identify repeated delamination patterns in these laminates. However, the “top hat” delamination style described by Chester et al [9] was evident from the time of flight data. The $[0_3/90_6/0_3]_S$ specimens did exhibit a consistent behavior. Major delaminations occurred at the ply changes immediately above and below the middle 0_6 layers. Smaller areas of damage could be found directly beneath the impact site at the first fiber angle change. The size of the damage area was found to be comparable for the two lay-ups impacted at similar velocities. Panels A and B in figure 5 are $[(0/90)_5/0]_S$ and $[0_3/90_6/0_3]_S$ laminates impacted at speeds of 310 m/s and 300 m/s respectively. The overall shape of the damage area for these two types of specimens was found to differ slightly. While plate B has an elliptic shape, the greater number of direction changes in the $[(0/90)_5/0]_S$ specimens resulted in a more defined cross-shaped pattern.

Figure 3. Load histories of instrumented specimens

Figure 4. C-scans of instrumented impact specimens

Figure 5. Comparison of [(0/90)5/0]_s and [03/90₆/03]_s specimens

Figure 6. Quasi-isotropic specimens

Figure 7. Locations of delaminations

In the case of impacting quasi-isotropic laminates it was found that the [(0/-45/90/+45)₂]_s laminates displayed much smaller damage areas than the other two quasi isotropic plates. This is illustrated in figure 6 where plates A and B are [(0/-45/90/+45)₂]_s laminates impacted at 260 and 270 m/s. Plates C and D are [0₃/-45₃/90₃/+45₃]_s specimens impacted at 260 and 275 m/s. This same result was found in the drop tower experiments of Dost et al [14]. While the [0₃/-45₃/+45₃/90₃]_s, and [0₃/-45₃/90₃/+45₃]_s did result in comparable damage areas, some differences in delamination were found. Figure 7 depicts edge views of the two types of laminates to illustrate delamination characteristics. The six interfaces where ply directions change are indicated with shaded lines. Delaminations occurring in the specimens are shown in bold. It was found that neither specimen tended to delaminate at the second of the six interfaces. Furthermore , the [0₃/-45₃/90₃/+45₃]_s laminates contained large delaminations at the third interface, while the [0₃/-45₃/+45₃/90₃]_s plates demonstrated very little damage here. Delamination patterns were somewhat varied for the lower interfaces of the two laminates. Clearly, the lay-up sequence for some families of laminates has a correlation to delamination initiation.

The visible failure for undamaged [0₃/90₆/03]_s and [(0/90)5/0]_s specimens in the compression after impact fixture was kinking and crushing of the material. This occurred near the top of the fixture, at the portion of the specimen edge that is unsupported. Failure was generally instantaneous with no forewarning. From the crushed region delaminations extended downwards into the panel as in Figure 8-A. Plate B demonstrates an interesting result of this investigation. It was found that the CAI failure of impacted [(0/90)5/0]_s panels was independent of the impact damage. Again, failure occurred near the top of the specimen and worked its way downward. The impact induced delaminations did not propagate and there was no difference in compressive strength when compared to undamaged specimens.

Results were different for the [0₃/90₆/03]_s laminates. Figure 9-A depicts a [0₃/90₆/03]_s laminate which has been damaged from an impact of 280 m/s. No surface damage was created, but two major delaminations were detected by c-scan. When specimens such as this were given CAI

tests, the growth of delaminations was evident as audible cracking. After failure, surface cracks extending towards the area of impact were visible at the specimen edge. C-scan results showed that the impact induced delaminations had grown across the entire width of the plate. Panel 9-B depicts the damage in the plate after it has been tested with the CAI fixture. The panels with detailed Teflon[®] inclusions exhibited the same type of failure as impacted specimens. Plate 9-C is a specimen containing Teflon[®] implants to simulate the damage in plate 9-A. Its failure in compression after impact is shown in plate 9-D. The primary difference between the CAI tests of impacted and simulated panels is that the Teflon[®] delaminations propagated to a greater degree than natural delaminations, and did so at lower load levels. The typical compressive strength reduction of the laminates due to impact damage was 25 to 40 percent. When panels with simulated delaminations were tested the strength reductions were consistently more, from 50 to 60 percent.

Figure 8. Undamaged vs. Impacted CAI Tests

Figure 9. Impacted vs. Simulated CAI Tests

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Studies conducted thus far show that manganin gages allow one to obtain brief normal stress histories at interfaces within composite materials. Specific laminates were found to have their own delamination and CAI characteristics. Further work will involve multiple gages within a specimen to compare the ply stresses at interfaces where the laminates tend to and tend not to delaminate. This should provide further insight as to the criteria governing formation of these delaminations. The use of Teflon[®] inserts to simulate delamination damage successfully imitated the failure of impacted specimens in compression after impact tests. However, the strength reduction of the panels containing implants far exceeded that of impacted specimens when compared to CAI tests on undamaged laminates.

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REFERENCES

- 1 Steiner, K. V., "Defect Classifications in Composites Using Ultrasonic Nondestructive Evaluation Techniques," *Damage Detection in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 1128*, J. E. Masters, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1992, pp. 72-84.
- 2 Anders, Oswald U., "Ultrasonic C-Scan as an Affordable Technique to Quantitatively Assess Damages in Laminate Composite Materials", *Proceedings from the 23rd International SAMPE Technical Conference*, 1991
- 3 Hagemaiier, D.J. ; Fassbender, R.H. "Ultrasonic Inspection of Carbon-Epoxy Composites", ASNT April 1985.
- 4 Daniel, I.M. ; Wooh, S.-C. "Deformation and Damage of Composite Laminates Under Impact Loading" *Impact Response and Elastodynamics of Composites ASME AMD Vol 116*, 1990 11-26.
- 5 Cantwell, W.J.; Morton, J."Comparison of the Low and High Velocity Impact Response of CFRP," *Composites*, Vol. 20, No.6, Nov. 1989 p. 545-551.
- 6 Cantwell, W.J. "Influence of Fiber Stacking Sequence on the High Velocity Impact Response of CFRP," *Journal of Materials Science Letters*, Vol.7, No.7, Jul 1988, p 756-758.
- 7 Malvern, L. E., Sun, C. T., and Liu, D., "Delamination Damage in Central Impacts at Subperforation Speeds on Laminated Kevlar/Epoxy Plates," *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture, Second Volume, ASTM STP 1012*, Paul A. Lagace, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1989, pp. 387-405.
- 8 Reddy, A. D. Rehfield, L. W. and Haag, R.S., "Influence of Prescribed Delaminations on Stiffness-Controlled Behavior of Composite Laminates," *Effects of Defects in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 836*, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1984
- 9 Chester, R.J. and Clark, G. "Modelling of Impact Damage Features in Graphite/Epoxy Laminates," *Damage Detection in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 1128*, J. E. Masters, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1992, pp. 200-212.
- 10 Sun, C.T. ; Jih, C.J. ; "Mechanics of Delamination in Composite Laminates Subject to Low Velocity Impact" *Impact Response and Elastodynamics of Composites ASME AMD Vol 116*, 1990 pp. 1-10.
- 11 Wu, H.T. and Springer, G.S. "Measurements of Matrix Cracking and Delamination Caused by Impact on Composite Plates," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.22, No.6, June 1988, pp. 518-532.
- 12 Dost, E. F., Ilcewicz, L. B., Avery, W. B., and Coxon, B. R. "Effects of Stacking Sequence on Impact Damage Resistance and Residual Strength for Quasi-Isotropic Laminates," *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture (Third Volume)*, *ASTM STP 1110*, T. K. O'Brien, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1991, pp. 476-500.
- 13 Bennet, Langdon, "Experimental Investigation of Exothermic Reactions During Shock Loading", Phd Thesis, North Carolina State Univeristy, 1992
- 14 Klang, E.C. ; Dellinger, G.A.; Kuo, T.M. "Impact Response of 3-D Woven and Laminated Composites", presented at The Fifth Conference on Advanced Engineering Fibers and Textiles Structures for Composites, Raleigh, North Carolina October 15 - 17, 1991.
- 15 Measurements Group, Inc., Micro-measurements Division, P.O. Box 27777, Raleigh, NC. 27611, USA (919) 365-3800.
- 16 Sonix Inc., 8700 Morrisette Drive, Springfield, VA 22152, USA (703) 440-0222